

A NOVEL HERBAL FACIAL CREAM FORMULATED WITH VITIS VINIFERA EXTRACT

T. Arun Kumar^{*1}, K. Sravan Kumar¹, B. Pravachana¹, S. D. Samreen¹, Ch. Asha¹,
K. Aneela²

¹NRK & KSR Gupta College of Pharmacy, IV B. Pharmacy.

²Department Pharmaceutical Analysis.

Article Received on 27 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 17 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 01 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18811267>

*Corresponding Author

T. Arun Kumar

NRK & KSR Gupta College of
Pharmacy, IV B. Pharmacy.

How To Cite This Article: T. Arun Kumar^{*1}, K. Sravan Kumar¹, B. Pravachana¹, S. D. Samreen¹, Ch. Asha¹, K. Aneela². (2026). A Novel Herbal Facial Cream Formulated With Vitis Vinifera Extract. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(3), 632–657.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

This investigation reports the formulation and evaluation of an herbal microencapsulated cream containing grape seed oil extract, a potent natural antioxidant widely used in skincare applications. Microencapsulation was achieved using a high-energy emulsification technique, with four formulations prepared at varying grape seed oil concentrations (3–4%). Characterization studies showed spherical, smooth microcapsules with particle sizes increasing proportionally to oil concentration, as confirmed by SEM analysis. The optimized microencapsulation (F3) was incorporated into a cream base and evaluated at different concentrations for physicochemical properties, antioxidant activity, and stability. All formulations demonstrated suitable pH and acceptable topical characteristics, while formulation F4 exhibited optimal viscosity, spreadability, and the highest in-vitro antioxidant activity. Stability studies confirmed good physical stability over

two months. Overall, the findings highlight the potential of microencapsulated grape seed oil as a stable, effective antioxidant system for advanced cosmeceutical and therapeutic skincare formulations.

KEYWORDS: Grape seed oil, Microencapsulation, Cream, Herbal formulation, Antioxidant, Semisolid dosage form.

INDEX

CHAPTER NO	CONTENTS
1.	INTRODUCTION
2.	ANATOMY AND FUNCTION OF SKIN
3.	ANTI-AGING
4.	MICROENCAPSULATION
5.	AIM & OBJECTIVES
6.	DRUG PROFILE
7.	METHODOLOGY
8.	FORMULATION AND MICROENCAPSULATION
9.	RESULTS
10.	DISCUSSION
11.	CONCLUSION
12.	REFERENCES

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE NO	TITLE
1.	FORMULATION OF MICROENCAPSULATION
2.	FORMULATION OF CREAM BASE
3.	PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF GRAPE SEED EXTRACT
4.	DETERMINATION TOTAL PHENOLIC CONTENT
5.	PARTICLE SIZE OF MICROENCAPSULATION (F1-F4)
6.	ORGANOLEPTIC PROPERTIES OF THE CREAM (F1-F2)
7.	PH OF CREAMS (F1-F5)
8.	VISCOSITY OF CREAMS (F1-F5)
9.	SPREADABILITY OF CREAM (F1-F5)
10.	STABILITY STUDIES FOR OPTIMIZED FORMULATION OF CREAM

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE NO	TITLE
1.	STRUCTURE OF THE SKIN
2.	DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE MICROSPHERES AND MICROCAPSULES
3.	Phytochemical screening tests for constituents of grape seed extract.
4.	Standard calibration curve of gallic acid.
5.	Particle size analysis of microencapsulation (F1-F4).
6.	SEM image of optimized formulation F3 at 220KX magnification
7.	SEM image of optimized formulation F3 at 330KX magnification
8.	O/W type of cream of formulation F1-F5.
9.	pH of cream (F1-F5).
10.	Viscosity of cream (F1-F5).
11.	Spreadability of cream (F1-F5).

INTRODUCTION

1. Skin is one of the most vital organs of the human body. Both women and men generally desire clear, bright, and healthy-looking skin. Consequently, with the rapid growth of the cosmetic industry, there is an increasing demand for products that promote skin brightness and provide anti-aging benefits. The skin is one of the most easily accessible organs of the body and serves as the primary route for topical drug delivery systems. Cosmetics are a class of health and beauty products used to care for the face and body, as well as to enhance or alter an individual's appearance. In addition to improving appearance, cosmetics play an important role in skin and body care and are also used to impart fragrance. Although cosmetics are widely recognized for their role in skin and body maintenance, they include a wide range of products designed for specific and significant purposes. Moreover, cosmetics are used in daily life by people of various races and cultures around the world.

2. Aging is a multifaceted biological process influenced by both intrinsic factors, such as genetics, and extrinsic factors originating from the environment. Among these external influences, free radicals play a significant role in the ageing process. They greatly affect ageing by inducing oxidative stress, which leads to cellular damage.

3. The antioxidant properties of grape seed oil offer an effective way to utilize grape seed waste and create cosmetic products for skin care, particularly for facial applications. At present, the use of cosmetics is steadily increasing, especially those containing antioxidants that help neutralize free radicals and prevent premature ageing of the skin.

4. Both patients and physicians often prefer creams rather than ointments, as creams are easier to apply, spread evenly, and wash off.

5. Creams are classified into two types: oil-in-water (O/W) creams and water-in-oil (W/O) creams. Oil-in-water creams are easier to wash off with water, feel less greasy on the skin, and are commonly used for cosmetic purposes, especially for facial application.

6. *Vitis vinifera* (grape) seed extracts are known to help reduce oxidative stress and promote healthier, brighter skin. These extracts are rich in bioactive polyphenols, particularly flavonoids, which have been widely reported to exhibit strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-aging, and skin-brightening effects.^[15,16,17] Because of these diverse biological activities, flavonoid-rich extracts are frequently incorporated into cosmetic skincare formulations.

7. Based on the explanation above, an oil-in-water (O/W) facial cream formulation was developed using grape seed oil as the active antioxidant ingredient. The formulation employed stearic acid as an emulsifier at various concentrations, and the resulting cream demonstrated good quality and physical stability.

ANATOMY AND FUNCTION OF THE SKIN

1.1 Anatomy and function of the skin

The skin is also known as integumentary system, it is the largest organ in humans' body, measuring 2 m² on the surface and 3.6 kg weight in adults. It functions as an insulating, waterproof barrier to insulate the body from the shocks of the environment. In addition, it generates antimicrobial peptides that inhibit infections as well as hormones, neuropeptides, and cytokines that have biological effects on the skin and body as a whole.

The underlying mesenchyme and the surface ectodermal layer give rise to the integumentary system. It is made up of the skin, appendages, and their derived structures, such as the sebaceous and sweat glands, nails, and hair follicles. Dermis, hypodermis, and epidermis are the three layers that make up the skin. It acts as a vital link between the body and the outside world, maintaining vital functions including temperature control, hydration and fat storage, protection, and the preservation of water and electrolytes. It also plays a significant part in the immunological and endocrine systems.

Fig. 1: Structure of the skin.

1.1.1 Epidermis

The epidermis is divided into four main layers based on the morphology and function of the keratinocytes

1. Basal layer (Stratum Basale).
2. Prickle cell layer (Stratum Spinosum).
3. Granular cell layer (Stratum Granulosum).

4. Cornified layer (Corneum).

1.1.2 Dermis

In contrast to the densely packed keratinocytes of the epidermis, the dermis is characterized by a more complex and dispersed arrangement of cells and components.

1. Cell in the dermis

- a) Fibroblasts.
- b) Immune and inflammatory cells.
- c) Nervous tissue.
- d) Blood vessels.

2. Extracellular matrix components

- a) collagen.
- b) Elastin.

1.1.3 Hypodermis

The subcutaneous layer underneath the dermis is called the hypodermis, and most of it is made up of fat. It shields the body from the cold, helps absorb trauma, and serves as the primary structural support for the skin. Nerves and blood vessels are entwined inside it.

ANTI-AGING

1.2 Anti-aging

The aging process is classified into two types

They are

1. Sequential skin aging.
2. Photo aging.

Both types have distinct clinical and historical features. Sequential skin aging is universal and a predictable process characterized by physiological alteration in skin function. In the aging process keratinocytes are unable to form a functional stratum corneum and rate of formation from neutral lipids slows down, resulting in dry pale skin with wrinkles. In contrast, photo aging is caused by over exposure to UV rays from sunlight. It is characterized by dry, pale and shallow skin, displaying fine wrinkles as well as deep furrows caused by the disorganization of epidermal and dermal components associated with elastosis and

Heliodermatitis. Herbs and plants have already proved useful as a tool in complementary medicine. Here's a brief overview of the categories mentioned.

1. Biological factors.
2. Environmental factors.
3. Mechanical factors.
4. Metabolism and Physiological factors.

1.2.1 Causes of aging

Aging can be caused by various factors including metabolic damage, cellular senescence, cellular death, and toxic and non-toxic garbage accumulation. Metabolic damage involves glycation, mitochondrial damage, and respiratory chain dysfunction, which generate free radicals and contribute to aging. Respiratory chain dysfunction accumulates various ageing phenotypes.

Generation, leading to tumor proliferation. Most causes of senescence are due to induction of tumor suppression genes p53 and p19Arf, while Skp2 E3-ubiquitin ligase can induce cancer. Inflammation can induce cellular senescence and death, including DNA damage, telomerase shortening, inadequate anti-oxidant systems, DNA repair and autophagy, defective cell cycle control, and defective proteasomes, lysosomes and shock proteins. Advanced glycation end products, cortisol and lipofuscin.

Solar radiation, primarily from the ultraviolet (UV) region, can cause harmful effects on the skin. UVA, UVB, and UVC are the three UV regions, with UVC being filtered out by the atmosphere. UVB, not completely filtered by the ozone layer, causes sunburn and pyrimidine dimer damage.

UVA radiation penetrates deeper skin layers, causing premature skin aging and free radical generation. UVB radiation causes 65% of skin damage. Exposure to UV radiation can lead to photo aging, sunburn, and skin cancer, highlighting the importance of avoiding sun exposure. radiation can lead to photo aging, sunburn, and skin cancer, highlighting the importance of avoiding sun exposure.

1.3 MICROENCAPSULATION

Microencapsulation is the process in which small droplets or particles of liquid or solid material are surrounded or coated by a continuous film of polymeric materials. Microencapsulation is defined as a process in which tiny particles or droplets are surrounded by a coating or embedded in a homogeneous or heterogeneous matrix, to give small capsules with many useful properties. Microcapsules are a modern dosage form which has been widely used to improve the stability of active substances or for any other medical purposes. Microencapsulation can provide a physical barrier between the core compound and the other components of the product. It is a technique by which liquid droplets, solid particles or gas compounds are entrapped into thin films of a food-grade microencapsulating agent.

Fig. 2: Difference between the Microspheres and Microcapsules.

1.1.1 ADVANTAGES

- * Controlled & Sustained Release.
- * Protection from Environment.
- * Taste and Odor Masking.
- * Targeted Delivery.
- * Conversion of Liquids to Solids.

1.3.2 DISADVANTAGES

- * High Manufacturing Costs.
- * Complexity in Scale-up.
- * Low Loading Capacity.
- * Potential for dose dumping.
- * Environmental Concerns.

1.3.3 Techniques of Microencapsulation

They are classified into three types they are

1. Physical

These rely primarily on mechanical or physical processes for encapsulation.

- Spray drying

A solution or suspension containing the core material is sprayed into hot air, rapidly drying the droplets and forming microcapsules.

- Solvent evaporation

The core material is dissolved or dispersed in a volatile solvent along with a polymer. The solvent is then evaporated, leaving behind solid microcapsules.

2. Chemical

These involve chemical reactions to form the capsule wall around the core material.

- In situ polymerization

Polymer forms directly on the surface of the core material via chemical reaction in the same phase.

- Interfacial polymerization

Polymer forms at the interface of two immiscible phases (usually oil and water), encapsulating the core material in the process.

- Suspension polymerization

Monomer droplets containing the core are suspended in a continuous phase, and polymerization occurs within those droplets.

- Emulsion polymerization

A fine emulsion of monomer and core material is polymerized, usually in an aqueous phase, to form microcapsules.

3. Physical-chemical

These methods combine physical and chemical processes.

- Coacervation

A polymer-rich phase separates from a solution and deposits around the core, forming a capsule upon solidification.

- Sol-gel method

Involves the transition of a solution (sol) into a solid (gel), entrapping the core material within the formed matrix.

1.3.4 APPLICATIONS

1. Pharmaceutical Industry.
2. Food Industry.
3. Cosmetics and Personal care.
4. Agrochemical Industry.
5. Textile Industry.
6. Paints and Coatings.
7. Printing and Paper Industry.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

The aim of the present study is to formulate and evaluate of anti-aging cream using grape seed extract by microencapsulation method.

OBJECTIVE

1. Extraction of grape seed.
2. Phytochemical analysis of grape seed extract.
3. Formulation of microcapsules.
4. Pre formulation studies of extract.
5. Incorporation of microcapsules into cream.
6. Evaluation of cream.
7. Determination of Antiaging factor.
8. Stability studies as per ICH guidelines.

DRUG PROFILE

Drug Profile

Name of the Drug: *Vitis vinifera* (Grape) Extract

Common Name: Grape extract / Grape seed extract

Biological Source: *Vitis vinifera* L.

Family: Vitaceae.

Chemical Constituents (Active Phytochemicals)

- *Vitis vinifera* is rich in polyphenolic compounds, mainly:
- Proanthocyanidins (OPCs).
- Resveratrol.

- Flavonoids, Tannins
- Phenolic acids.
- Vitamin E and Vitamin C (trace amounts).

Category

- Natural antioxidant.
- Herbal cosmetic active.
- Anti-aging and skin-protective agent.

Mechanism of Action (Cosmetic/Topical Use)

- Antioxidant activity: Neutralizes free radicals and reduces oxidative stress on skin.
- Anti-aging effect: Prevents collagen degradation and improves skin elasticity.
- Anti-inflammatory action: Reduces skin irritation and redness.
- Photoprotective effect: Protects skin from UV-induced damage.
- Moisturizing support: Enhances skin barrier function when formulated in creams.

Therapeutic / Cosmetic Uses

- Anti-aging facial creams.
- Skin rejuvenation products.
- Moisturizing and nourishing creams.
- Acne-prone and sensitive skin formulations.
- Sunscreen and after-sun products.

Dose / Concentration (Topical)

- Typical concentration in cosmetic formulations: 0.5% – 5% w/w.
- Optimal concentration depends on extract potency and formulation stability.

Solubility

- Water (hydroalcoholic extracts).
- Ethanol.
- Propylene glycol.
- Poorly soluble in oils (unless specially processed).

Physical Description

- Appearance: Brown to reddish-brown powder or liquid extract.

- Odor: Mild, characteristic.
- Taste: Astringent (not relevant for topical use).

Stability

- Sensitive to:
- Light.
- Heat.
- Oxidation.
- Stability improved by:
- Antioxidants (e.g., vitamin E).
- Opaque containers.
- Controlled pH (5.0–6.5).

pH Compatibility

- Ideal pH for facial cream: 5.5 – 6.5.
- Compatible with normal skin pH.

Safety Profile

- Generally recognized as safe for topical use.
- Non-toxic and non-irritant at recommended concentrations.
- Patch test recommended before large-scale use.

Role in Facial Cream Formulation

- Active herbal ingredient.
- Provides antioxidant and anti-aging benefits.
- Enhances cosmetic appeal as a natural ingredient.
- Supports marketing claims (herbal, natural, anti-aging).

Evaluation Parameters for *Vitis vinifera* Facial Cream

- Physical appearance.
- pH determination.
- Spreadability.
- Viscosity.
- Homogeneity.

- Washability.
- Skin irritation test.
- Stability studies.
- Antioxidant activity (optional).

Storage Conditions

- Store in a cool, dry place.
- Protect from direct sunlight.
- Use airtight containers.

METHODOLOGY

1. Authentication of *Vitis vinifera* seed (Grape seed)

Grapes (*Vitis vinifera*) were collected from the local market of Guntur. The seeds were manually separated from the fruits, thoroughly washed, and dried under sunlight. The dried seeds were then authenticated by the Central Ayurveda Research Institute (CARI), Guntur.

2. Extraction of grape seed

The grape seeds were thoroughly washed and dried under sunlight. Oil extraction was carried out using the cold pressing method. In this process, the dried grape seeds were mechanically pressed to obtain the oil without the application of heat. The extracted grape seed oil was then collected and stored in a cool, dark place until further use.

3. Phytochemical analysis of extracts

1. Steroids: An aliquot of the seed extract 1ml was dissolved in 10 ml of chloroform and equal volume of concentrated sulfuric acid was added by sides of the test tube. The upper layer turns to red color and sulfuric layer showed yellow with green fluorescence. This indicated the presence of steroids.

2. Tannins: An aliquot of the seed extract 2ml was added to few drops of 1% lead acetate and the yellowish precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

3. Saponins: An aliquot of the seed extract 5ml was mixed with 20 ml of distilled water in a graduated cylinder and then agitated for 15 minutes. Formation of foam indicates the presence of saponins.

4. Anthocyanins: An aliquot of the seed extract 2ml was added to 2 ml of 2N HCl and ammonia. The appearance of pink-red which turns to blue-violet indicates the presence of anthocyanins.

5. Glycosides: 2ml glacial acetic acid one drop of 5% FeCl₃ and concentrated H₂SO₄ was added in to 5ml of extract the appearance of brown ring indicates the presence of glycosides.

6. Alkaloids: A Mayer's test: - To the acidic solution, Mayer's reagent (Potassium mercuric iodide solution) was added. Cream colored precipitate indicates presence of alkaloids.

7. Phenol: ½ ml of FeCl₃ solution was added into 2 ml of test solution, formation of an intense color indicates the presence of phenol.

8. Flavonoids: An aliquot of the seed extract 2-3ml and few drops of sodium hydroxide solution were added into a test-tube. Formation of intense yellow color that became colorless on addition of few drops of dilute HCl indicates the presence of flavonoids. Own ring indicates the presence of glycosides.

b) Quantitative analysis

I. Determination of Total Phenolic Content

Preparation of Standard solution

Approximately 10 mg of Gallic acid was weighed and transferred in to a (10 µg/ml) volumetric flask. Gallic acid dissolved in small amount of methanol in a volumetric flask and made up the volume up to 10 ml by using the methanol to prepare 1000 µg/ml solution. From the above stock solution, 1ml was pipetted in to a volumetric flask of 10 ml capacity and volume was made by using distilled water to 10ml (100 µg /ml). Pipetted out 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml of 2nd stock solution and transfer in to the 10 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made to 10 ml to get the concentration 10 go/ml to 50 µg/ml. Then 0.2ml of Folin-Ciocalteu phenol reagent, 0.5 ml of saturated sodium carbonate was added and volume was made up to 10ml with distilled water to get the concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 µg/ml respectively. The standard solution was placed in a dark place for 1 hour and absorbance was measured at 636 nm using Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Sample solution

10mg of extract was transferred into 10ml of volumetric flask. Extract was dissolved with small amount of methanol and volume was made up to 10ml by using methanol to prepare

1000 µg/ml solution. From the above stock solution, 1ml was pipetted out to a volumetric flask of 10ml capacity and volume was made up by using distilled water to prepare 100 µg/ml solution. 1 ml of above stock solution was pipette out and transferred into 10ml volumetric flask, 0.2 ml of Folin- Coalter phenol reagent was added and 0.5ml saturated sodium carbonate was also added and volume was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. Sample solutions were placed in a dark place for 1h and absorbance was measured at 636 nm using Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer.

ii . Determination of Total Flavonoid Content

5 gm of extract was transferred into beaker; 50 ml of distilled water was added and mixed well. Then 2 ml of Hal was added to a beaker and boiled on water bath for 30 minutes and 10 ml of ethyl acetate was added. Empty filter paper was weighed called as W1. Then extract was filtered and filter paper will absorb the Flavonoids. The above residue was discarded and filter paper was dried completely and weighed; the dried filter paper called as W2.

Total Flavonoid Content = $(W2 - W1) / \text{weight of the sample} \times 100$.

Preparation of Microencapsulation

Microencapsulation was carried out using the ionic gelation method.

Preparation of Microencapsulation

Sodium alginate was dissolved in water, with continuous magnetic stirring at 1700 rpm for 20 minutes. Then essential oil (Grape seed oil) was added in the solution with continuous stirring for 10 minutes. The oil phase was prepared separately.

Aqueous Phase

The aqueous phase was prepared by dissolving calcium chloride in a suitable quantity of water. The solution was transferred to a volumetric flask, and the final volume was made up to 100 mL using deionized water to obtain a clear and homogeneous solution.

Formulation of Microencapsulation

The prepared oil phase was added dropwise into the aqueous phase using a syringe under continuous stirring, leading to the formation of microcapsules. The mixture was stirred further at 1700 rpm for 15 minutes to ensure uniform microcapsule formation. The microcapsules were then collected by filtration using Whatman filter paper No. 1 (125 mm), washed 2–3 times with deionized water, and dried at room temperature.

Table No. 1: formulation of microencapsulation.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
Grape seed oil	3ml	3.5ml	3.8ml	4ml
Carbopol	1g	1.5g	1.8g	2g
Calcium lactate	16g	16g	16g	16g
Distilled water	Q. S	Q. S	Q.S	Q. S

Preparation of Cream Base

The oil phase, consisting of stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, and liquid paraffin, was taken in a beaker and melted over a water bath at 75 °C. In a separate beaker, glycerin, methyl paraben, and propylene glycol were dissolved in distilled water and heated on a water bath until completely dissolved to form the aqueous phase.

The molten oil phase was then added to the aqueous phase with continuous titration to form a homogeneous cream base. A few drops of rose oil were added as a perfume and mixed thoroughly. Finally, microencapsulated particles of suitable micro-range size were incorporated into the prepared cream base to obtain the final formulation.

Formulation Design and Rationale (F1–F5)

A series of five oil-in-water (O/W) cream formulations (F1–F5) were developed incorporating herbal microencapsulated grape seed oil. The formulations were designed with a gradual increase in microencapsulation concentration, along with proportional adjustments in emulsifying and consistency agents, to study their effect on physicochemical properties, stability, and performance of the cream system.

Glyceryl stearate was used as the primary emulsifying agent, while cetyl alcohol functioned as a consistency enhancer and co-emulsifier. The systematic variation from F1 to F5 allows comparative evaluation and identification of an optimized formulation suitable for topical application.

F1 – Low-Concentration Formulation

Formulation F1 contained the lowest level of herbal microencapsulation (1 g), along with minimal concentrations of glyceryl stearate (1.5 g) and cetyl alcohol (0.8 g). This formulation exhibited a light cream consistency with relatively low viscosity and occlusiveness.

Purpose

F1 served as the baseline formulation to study the influence of minimal microencapsulation incorporation on cream characteristics, including texture, spreadability, and stability.

F2 – Moderate-Concentration Formulation

Formulation F2 consisted of an increased microencapsulation content (1.5 g), supported by higher levels of glyceryl stearate (2 g) and cetyl alcohol (1 g). This resulted in improved emulsification efficiency and a moderate increase in viscosity.

Purpose

F2 was designed to evaluate the improvement in physical stability, texture, and skin feel with moderate enhancement of active content compared to the baseline formulation.

F3: Optimized Mid-Level Formulation

Formulation F3 incorporated 2 g of microencapsulation, with glyceryl stearate (2.5 g) and cetyl alcohol (1.2 g), producing a cream with balanced viscosity, good spreadability, and enhanced emollient properties.

Purpose

F3 is considered the optimized formulation, offering an ideal balance between stability, drug release potential, moisturizing effect, and consumer acceptability.

F4: High-Concentration Formulation: Formulation F4 contained a higher loading of microencapsulation (2.5 g), with corresponding increases in glyceryl stearate (3 g) and cetyl alcohol (1.4 g). This formulation showed increased thickness, viscosity, and occlusive behavior.

Purpose

F4 was developed to assess formulation performance at higher active loading and to study the impact on spreadability and sensory characteristics.

F5 – Maximum-Concentration Formulation

Formulation F5 represented the highest concentration level, containing 3 g of microencapsulation, 3.5 g of glyceryl stearate, and 1.6 g of cetyl alcohol. The formulation exhibited maximum viscosity and active content.

Purpose

F5 was used to determine the upper incorporation limit of herbal microencapsulation and to evaluate potential formulation challenges such as reduced spreadability and increased greasiness.

Overall Significance

The progressive design of formulations F1–F5 provides a structured approach to understanding the effect of microencapsulation concentration on cream performance. This comparative formulation strategy is valuable for identifying an optimized topical delivery system and supports further evaluation of stability, release behavior, and therapeutic efficacy.

Table No. 2: Formulation of cream base.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	Category
Microencapsulation	1g	1.5g	2g	2.5g	3g	Drug delivery/formulation technique.
Glyceryl stearate	1.5g	2g	2.5g	3g	3.5g	Emulsifying agents/stabilizer.
Cetyl alcohol	0.8g	1g	1.2g	1.4g	1.6g	Emollient/thickening agent.
Mineral oil	1.16ml	1.16ml	1.16ml	1.16ml	1.1ml	Emollient/occlusive agent.
Butylene glycol	1.26ml	1.26ml	1.26ml	1.26ml	1.26ml	Humectant/solvent.
Potassium sorbate	0.05g	0.05g	0.05g	0.05g	0.05g	Preservative.
Propylene glycol	6.2ml	6.2ml	6.2ml	6.2ml	6.2ml	Solvent/humectant/penetration enhancer.
Perfume	2drops	2drops	2drops	2drops	2drops	Fragrance agent.
Distilled water	Q. S	Vehicle/solvent.				

7.1 Particle Size Determination

The particle size distribution and mean diameter of the microencapsulates were evaluated using an optical microscope. A stage micrometer was employed to calibrate the eyepiece micrometer. Ten divisions of the stage micrometer were matched against the corresponding divisions of the eyepiece micrometer, and the calibration factor was calculated.

The size of the microcapsules was determined by multiplying the number of divisions occupied by a particle in the eyepiece micrometer by the calibration factor. A total of 30 microcapsules were randomly selected, and their individual sizes were measured to determine the particle size distribution and mean particle diameter.

7.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis

The morphology of the grape seed oil microcapsules was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Prior to imaging, the microcapsules were coated with gold and observed

under a Nova NanoSEM (NPEP303) at an applied voltage of 5.00 kV. Photomicrographs were captured and analyzed using ImageJ software to study the surface characteristics and structural features of the microcapsules.

8. Evaluation of cream

8.1 Organoleptic properties

The cream thus obtained was evaluated for its organoleptic properties like color, odor and texture. The appearance of the cream was judged by its color and roughness.

8.2 Dye test

The Scarlet red dye is mixed with the cream. Place a drop of the cream on a microscopic slide then covers it with a cover slip, and examines it under a microscope. If the disperse globules appear red the ground colorless then its w/o type. The reverse condition occurs its o/w type cream i.e. the disperse globules appear colorless and ground red.

8.3 pH determination

The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solution. pH electrode was dipped in to the cream and its pH was measured with the help of digital pH meter.

8.4 Viscosity determination

Viscosity measurement was carried out by placing the preparation in a 100 ml glass beaker and selecting the spindle number 64 at 10 rpm and maintained at temperature at 25 °C. The measurement was carried out thrice by using a Brookfield Viscometer.

8.5 Spread ability

Spread ability of formulated cream was measured by placing sample in between two slides then compressed to uniform thickness by placing a definite weight for defined time. The specified time required to separate the two slides was measured as spread ability. Spread ability was calculated by the following formula

$$\text{Spreadability} = ML/T$$

Were,

M = Weight tied to the upper slide

L = Length of glass slide T = Time taken in seconds.

Stability Studies

Stability studies of the optimized cream formulation (F4) were conducted according to ICH guidelines. The formulation was stored in airtight glass containers and subjected to accelerated conditions at 40 ± 2 °C and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity in a stability chamber for a period of 2 months. Samples were withdrawn at 1 and 2 months and evaluated for physical characteristics including color, odor, pH, viscosity, and phase separation to assess formulation stability.

RESULTS

5.1 Phytochemical analysis of extract

A. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

Table 3: Phytochemical analysis of grape seed extract.

SL.NO	PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUTION	OIL EXTRACT OF GRAPE SEED
1.	Steroids	++
2.	Tannins	+++
3.	Saponins	++
4.	Anthocyanins	-
5.	Glycosides	++
6.	Alkaloids	++
7.	Flavonoids	+++

Phytochemical screening tests for constituents of grape seed extract (oil extract). (+++), (++) , (+) and (-) refer to high, moderate, low and absent amount respectively.

Fig 3: Phytochemical screening tests for constituents of grape seed extract.

B. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

1). Determination of Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content was determined by measuring the absorbance of the sample solution at a wavelength of 636 nm. Quantification was carried out by comparison with a gallic acid standard calibration curve, which showed excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.9991$). The total phenolic content of the samples was calculated from the calibration curve, and the results are presented in Table 6 and Figure 16.

Table 4: Determination total phenolic content.

SAMPLES	CONCENTRATIONS($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	ABSORBANCE
Gallic acid (standard)	10	0.265 \pm 0.009
	20	0.481 \pm 0.015
	30	0.714 \pm 0.021
	40	0.997 \pm 0.026
	50	1.178 \pm 0.046
Grape seed oil extract	10	0.710 \pm 0.017

Fig 4: Standard calibration curve of gallic acid.

2). Determination of Total Flavonoid Content

The total flavonoid content of grape seed oil was determined using the filter paper method. The flavonoid content was calculated using the appropriate formula, and the total flavonoid content was found to be 24.10%.

5.2 CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROENCAPSULATION

5.2.1 PARTICLE SIZE

Table 5: Particle size of Microencapsulation (F1-F4).

SL.NO	FORMULATION	PARTICLE SIZE (μm) (Mean \pm SD)
1.	F1	39 \pm 2.47
2.	F2	42.25 \pm 2.29
3.	F3	34.5 \pm 0.70
4.	F4	39.25 \pm 1.59

Fig. 5: Particle size analysis of microencapsulation (F1-F4).

5.2.2 SEM (SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY) ANALYSIS

Fig 6: SEM image of optimized formulation F3 at 220KX magnification.

Fig. 7: SEM image of optimized formulation F3 at 330KX magnification.

5.3 EVALUATION PARAMETER OF CREAM

5.3.1 ORGANOLEPTIC PROPERTIES

Table 6: Organoleptic properties of the cream (F1-F2).

SL.NO	PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	Colour	White	White	White	White	White
2.	Odour	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3.	Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

Dye Test

The dye test was performed by mixing Scarlet red dye with the cream sample. A drop of the dyed cream was placed on a microscopic slide, covered with a cover slip, and examined under a microscope. The dispersed globules appeared red, while the continuous phase remained colorless, indicating that the cream was of the oil-in-water (o/w) type.

Fig. 8: O/W type of cream of formulation F1-F5.

5.3.2 pH DETERMINATION

Table No. 7: pH of creams (F1-F5).

SL.NO	FORMULATION	pH*(Mean \pm SD)
1.	F1	5.39 \pm 0.01
2.	F2	5.41 \pm 0.03
3.	F3	5.40 \pm 0.05
4.	F4	5.43 \pm 0.03
5.	F5	5.37 \pm 0.06

Fig. 9: pH of cream (F1-F5).

5.3.3 VISCOSITY DETERMINATION

Table No. 8: Viscosity of creams (F1-F5).

SL.NO	FORMULATIONS	VISCOSITY*(Cps)(Mean ± SD)
1.	F1	12433.33±204.28
2.	F2	14333.33±219.99
3.	F3	15500.00±235.70
4.	F4	11700.00±94.28
5.	F5	13333.33±157.13

Fig. 10: Viscosity of cream (F1-F5).

5.3.4 SPREADABILITY

Table 9: Spreadability of cream (F1-F5).

SL.N0	FORMULATION	SPREADABILITY* (g.cm/Sec) (Mean ± SD)
1.	F1	56.23±0.35
2.	F2	60.60±0.42
3.	F3	69.77±0.41
4.	F4	71.50±0.52
5.	F5	67.63±0.53

Fig. 11: Spreadability of cream (F1-F5).

5.3.5 STABILITY STUDIES

Table 10: Stability studies for optimized formulation of cream.

FORMULATIONS	PARAMETER	INITIAL	1 ST MONTH	2 ND MONTH
F4 (40°C ± 2°C & RH 75% ± 5%)	Colour	White	White	White
	Odour	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
	Phase separation	No separation	No separation	No separation
	pH	5.43±0.01	5.39±0.01	5.26±0.01
	Viscosity(cps)	11700.00±94.28	10366.67±78.56	9333.33±219.98

DISCUSSION

In the present study, an attempt was made to formulate and evaluate an anti-aging cream using grape seed oil (GSO) extract. Different concentrations of grape seed oil were incorporated into cream formulations to assess their influence on physicochemical properties, stability, and antioxidant activity. The cream formulations were successfully prepared using the emulsification method, with microencapsulation incorporated into the cream base to enhance stability and controlled release of the active ingredient.

Phytochemical analysis of grape seed oil demonstrated the presence of various bioactive compounds. Qualitative analysis confirmed multiple phytoconstituents, while quantitative estimation of total phenolic and flavonoid contents substantiated the antioxidant potential of grape seed oil. The total phenolic content was found to be 31.92 ± 0.01 mg/ml, and the total flavonoid content was 24.10%, indicating a strong antioxidant profile that supports its use in anti-aging formulations.

Particle size analysis demonstrated good stability of the microencapsulated systems, with particle sizes ranging from 34.5 ± 0.70 µm to 42.25 ± 2.29 µm. Among the formulations, F3 exhibited a favorable particle size distribution. Surface morphology studies using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) further confirmed the integrity and stability of the microencapsulation within the cream matrix.

All cream formulations exhibited acceptable organoleptic properties, appropriate pH values, good compatibility, and suitable viscosity. Spreadability varied among formulations, reflecting differences in composition and concentration of grape seed oil. In-vitro antioxidant studies revealed that formulation F4 exhibited the highest antioxidant activity, suggesting an optimal concentration of grape seed oil in this formulation.

Stability studies conducted on the optimized formulation F4 over a period of two months demonstrated good physical stability, with no significant changes in color, odor, or phase separation. Minor variations in pH and viscosity were observed but remained within acceptable limits. Overall, the findings of the study confirm that grape seed oil-based cream formulations are stable, antioxidant-rich, and hold significant potential for cosmetic and therapeutic applications.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully focused on the preparation and evaluation of an anti-aging cream containing grape seed oil using the microencapsulation technique. The effect of varying grape seed oil concentrations on formulation behavior was investigated while maintaining constant levels of other excipients. The prepared formulations were evaluated for dye test, organoleptic properties, pH, viscosity, spreadability, in-vitro antioxidant activity, and stability.

Microencapsulation studies demonstrated that particle size varied with oil concentration, with smaller and more uniform particle sizes observed in specific formulations. Surface morphology analysis using SEM confirmed the stability of the microencapsulation, particularly in formulation F3, indicating its suitability for topical application. All cream formulations exhibited acceptable organoleptic properties, appropriate pH, good compatibility, and suitable viscosity, while spreadability showed variation among formulations.

The dye test confirmed that all formulations, including the optimized formulation F4, were oil-in-water (o/w) type creams. In-vitro antioxidant studies revealed that formulation F4 exhibited the highest antioxidant activity. Stability studies conducted on formulation F4 over a period of two months demonstrated good physical stability, with only minor and acceptable variations in pH and viscosity.

Overall, the study concludes that grape seed oil extract, when formulated into a cream using the emulsification and microencapsulation method, exhibits promising antioxidant properties. These findings suggest that grape seed oil-based creams have significant potential for cosmetic and pharmaceutical applications, particularly in skincare. Further studies are recommended to evaluate long-term stability and therapeutic efficacy under real-world conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Fith KN, Nining, Syamsiyah R. Formulation and Development of Grape Seed Oil (*Vitis Vinifera* L) Emulgel Peel-Off Mask using Gelling Agent Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose (HPMC). *Earth and Environ. Sci.*, 2021; 755(1): 1-7.
2. Mackiewicz, Z., & Rimkevicius, A. (2008). Skin aging. *Gerontologija*, 9(2): 103-108.
3. Suhery, W. N., Fernando, A., & Has, N. (2016). Uji aktivitas antioksidan dari ekstrak bekatul padi ketan merah dan hitam (*Oryza sativa* L. var. *Glutinosa*) dan formulasinya dalam sediaan krim. *PHARMACY: Jurnal Farmasi Indonesia (Pharmaceutical Journal of Indonesia)*, 13(1): 101-115.
4. Ansel, H., Allen, L. & Popovich, N. (2011). *Bentuk Dosis Farmasi Ansel dan Sistem Pengiriman Obat*, Edisi 9. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, Balimore.
5. Syamsuni. (2006). *Farmasetka Dasar dan Hitungan Farmasi*. Penerbit Buku Kedokteran EGC, Jakarta.
6. Lotfollahi Z. The anatomy, physiology and function of all skin layers and the impact of ageing on the skin. *Wound Pract. Res.*, 2024; 32(1): 6-10
7. Eleanor RG, George FM. The pathophysiology of skin aging: New insights into an old dilemma. *Am. J. Pathol.*, 2020; 190(7): 1356-69.
8. Casey G. The physiology of the skin. *Nurs. Stand*, 2002; 16(34): 47-51.
9. Jia Z, Tang M, Wu J. The determination of flavonoid contents in mulberry and their scavenging effects on superoxide radicals. *Food Chem.*, 1999; 64: 555-59.
10. Krishna RG, Anita RP, Milind JU. Drug excipient compatibility testing protocols and characterization: A review. *Asian J. Chem. Sci.*, 2019; 6(3): 1-22.
11. Abhijit G, et.al. Formulation and Evaluation of Antiaging Ointment Containing Microencapsulated Turmeric and Jojoba Oil. *Int. J. Drug. Discov. Tech.*, 2023; 13(4): 1298-304.
12. Ishaan A, Shikha BC. Formulation and evaluation of anti-aging cream using grape powder. *Original Research Paper*, 2023; 13(5): 48-51.
13. Ojasvita AK, Kamal B, Pradnya G, Punam S, Vaishnavi G. Formulation and evaluation of anti-aging cream. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2023; 1(6): 39-46.
14. Sumaiyah S, Meyliana. Formulation and evaluation of skin anti-aging nanocream containing canola (*Brassica napus* L.) oil. *Indonesian J. Pharm. Clin. Res.*, 2021; 4(1): 47-58.
15. Blois MS. Antioxidant determinations by the use of a stable free radical. *Nanomed. Res. J.*, 2019; 4(4): 204-8.